

Analysis of the correlation between ASI and HIC for steel and concrete road restraint systems on different types of basements

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ABSTRACT

Run-off-road accidents counts for nearly one third of all fatalities in the European Union. To prevent errant vehicles from colliding with hazards on the road side, road restraint systems are positioned close to the edge of the carriageway. These road restraint systems shall reduce the risk of injuries to the occupants and have to fulfil the European standard EN 1317. However, the assessment criteria ASI and THIV are not developed to identify the injury risk. Thus some attempts have been made to correlate these criteria with metrics able to assess the injury risk e.g. HIC. The present study will increase the dataset of EN 1317 tests including calculation of ASI and HIC. A correlation function between ASI and HIC is calculated and compared to the literature.

INTRODUCTION

Even though the number of fatalities in single vehicle accidents (SVA) decreased between 2007 and 2013 in the European Union by 41%, the numbers kept almost constant between 2013 and 2016 [1]. 7,500 fatalities occurred in single vehicle accidents in 2016 which represents nearly one third of all fatalities. SVA include run-off-road collisions, collisions with fallen rocks or debris on the road, rollover crashes and collisions with animals [1]. One of the counter measures to avoid vehicles to run-off a road are road restraint systems (RRS). RRS are positioned next to the road to shield hazardous objects on the road side and to prevent vehicles from impacting these objects. The assessment of RRS in Europe is based on the European standard EN 1317 [2–4]. Three main criteria are evaluated: 1) the containment level, 2) the impact severity levels (ASI: Acceleration Severity Index, THIV: Theoretical Head Impact Velocity) and 3) the deformation expressed by the working width. Main criteria to evaluate the passenger's injury risk are ASI and THIV. However, ASI and THIV are more likely to be used to evaluate the barrier performance rather than to evaluate the injury risk [5]. Thus injury metrics should be related to injury mechanisms able to assess the injury risk, such as criterions are used in the automotive safety [6]. One commonly used injury metric is for instance the Head Injury Criterion (HIC) which was defined by Versace [7] based on the Gadd Severity Index [8–10] and is in use since 1972 [11].

To evaluate how ASI and THIV can be used as a predictor of injury risk some attempts have been made to calculate a correlation between ASI, THIV and HIC. Shojaati [12] used twelve physical guardrail tests for their conclusions. Anghileri et al. [5] analysed data from 23 TB11 vehicle tests and plotted ASI and THIV against HIC. No information is given which type of barrier was included in the analysis. Chell et al. [13] investigated 33 TB11 vehicle tests (28 guardrails and 5 concrete barriers) and analysed the correlation between ASI, THIV and HIC. Gabauer and Thompson [14] evaluated 24 full-scale crash tests at three different impact velocities (25, 30 and 35 mph) with a total number of 44 occupant responses (a number of tests had crash test dummies in the right and left front seats) available from National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA) ranging from an impact speed of 25 mph to 40 mph. Further studies used virtual simulations for their conclusions. Sturt and Fell [15] performed three physical tests against a concrete barrier for validation purposes and performed 50 Finite Element (FE) simulations. They varied impact speed from 90 km/h to 150 km/h and impact angle ranging from 15° to 25°. Klootwijk and Hoogvelt [16] used the multi body simulation program MADYMO to simulate 22 impact configurations against a guardrail with different vehicle speeds ranging from 35 km/h to 100 km/h and impact angles ranging from 5° to 35°.

Even though correlations could be identified between ASI, THIV and HIC almost every author concluded that further studies are necessary to develop appropriate correlation functions. Specifically the available dataset is not large enough to draw final conclusions [5] and further data of different laboratories are required [13].

OBJECTIVE

The objective was to evaluate the relation between ASI, THIV and HIC for different RRS (steel, concrete), containment levels, working widths and the TB11 vehicle class type according to the EN 1317.

METHOD

Test set-up and analysis matrix

The tests were performed according to EN 1317 specifications at the Graz University of Technology as an accredited test laboratory. For the evaluation of the impact severity, test data of passenger cars (TB11) equipped with a dummy, impacting restraint systems for different containment levels were used. In total 73 tests were available for analysis.

Data acquisition

Measurement were taken from one tri-axial transducer (manufacturer: ASC; type: 5411LN-100) with a measurement range of 100 g. Two further tri-axial transducers (manufacturer: Measurement Specialities; type: 1203-0500-10-240X) are used for redundancy reasons with a measurement range of 500 g. Further to this an angular velocity sensor (rate sensor) (manufacturer: IES; type: 3103-2400) is equipped in the vehicle. The maximum range of the velocity sensor is 2 400°/s. All of the transducers are mounted on a metal plate, which is mounted to the vehicle's centre of gravity. All the transducers are calibrated.

One tri-axial transducer (manufacturer: FPG, type: FA3109) was used in the center of gravity of the head of the anthropomorphic test device (ATD). As ATD a 50th percentile Hybrid III dummy was used.

For data acquisition a K3700 Minidau[®] (Mini Data Acquisition Unit) from Kayser-Threde with a sampling rate of 10 kHz was used.

Assessment

The assessment of the safety measures ASI and THIV is based on the EN 1317-2 [3]. The HIC₃₆ is calculated according to the definition in the FMVSS 208 (Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standard) of the NHTSA [17].

$$ASI(k) = \left[\left(\frac{\bar{A}_x}{12} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{A}_y}{9} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{A}_z}{10} \right)^2 \right]^{0.5} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$THIV = [V_x^2(T) + V_y^2(T)]^{0.5} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$HIC = \max \left[\frac{1}{t_2 - t_1} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} a(t) dt \right]^{2.5} (t_2 - t_1) \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

RESULTS

In Figure 1 test results of HIC₃₆ are plotted as function of ASI. The data is complemented with data available from literature. In order to show a correlation for each set of data corresponding exponential trend functions are added. For visibility reasons statistical outliers or tests in which the dummy head was hitting the restraint system (resulting in extremely high HIC-values) are not displayed. The data show a clear tendency of increasing ASI of lower containment towards to higher containment levels (R=0.84). This can be observed for concrete (R=0.46) and steel (R=0.96) RRS even though steel RRS show a much stronger correlation. For the HIC a correlation to a higher containment could not be observed to that extent (R=0.57). Steel RRS show a slight positive correlation of HIC and containment level (R=0.29) but concrete RRS do not show a clear picture (R=-0.13). Normal containment and low angle containment classes are excluded due to the low number of data. Higher containment and very high containment classes are considered in the analysis only.

Further there is a negative correlation observed for the ASI with increasing dynamic deflection ($R=-0.93$), whereby steel RRS show a slightly stronger correlation ($R=-0.88$) than concrete RRS ($R=-0.80$). For the HIC a negative correlation ($R=-0.78$) for all data was observed. Steel RRS show a much stronger negative correlation with increasing deflection ($R=-0.78$). When considering concrete RRS only, no correlation is observed ($R=0.01$).

Figure 1: HIC36 as function of ASI (test data + trendlines)

DISCUSSION

A tendency of increasing HIC with increasing ASI can be observed in the analysed dataset. This tendency can be identified in literature either. However, for the present data the gradient of the trend function is significantly lower compared to literature results. Shojaati [12] used steel RRS only and the gradient of the function is quite high ($R=0.84$). A high gradient was identified for the study of Sturt and Fell [15] ($R=0.93$) also but they analyse concrete RRS only. Both studies used a very small set of tests. The studies of Chell et al. [13] ($R=0.39$) and Anghileri [5] ($R=0.47$) are not that much different even the correlation seems to be stronger compared to our findings ($R=0.26$).

One reason for the deviation to the literature [5,12,13] might be the type of RRS analysed. Our dataset comprises an equal number of steel and concrete RRS test data. In the literature, in which this data is explicitly stated [13], the share of steel RRS is approximately 85% and 15% are concrete RRS.

Another influencing factor might be the type of basement (gravel, asphalt, bridge) on which the RRS is erected. For the steel systems in the present dataset there is an equal distribution between rammed RRS and RRS bolted to bridge decks. Only Chell et al. [13] provides this information but the share of RRS bolted to a bridge deck is significantly lower (9 out of 28).

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

For all tests available in the present data a positive correlation between ASI and HIC is observed ($R=0.46$) which is in line with available literature. However, the correlation found is significantly lower compared to other studies.

Considering the HIC as well established criterion for the head injury, the found values for the impacts on RRS (when disregarding outliers) are considerably lower than the proposed limit for severe head injury (50% risk of AIS3+ injury at $HIC36=1.000$ [17]). In approximately 5% of the tests the HIC was exceeding the limit i.e. dummy head contact with stiff structures.

APPENDIX - Analysed dataset

ID	Containment Level	Soil	Material	Dynamic Deflection [m]	Working Width Class	ASI [-]	THIV [km/h]	HIC [-]
1	T3	Asphalt	Concrete	0.1	W2	1.4	22.6	61
2	N2	Asphalt	Concrete	n.a.	n.a.	1.5	19.5	48
3	N2	Asphalt	Concrete	n.a.	n.a.	1.5	24.0	238
4	N2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.3	W1	1.4	20.1	104
5	N2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.2	W1	1.3	23.1	114
6	N2	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.3	W1	1.1	26.9	114
7	N2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.1	W2	1.2	22.7	176
8	N2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.5	W2	1.2	23.0	180
9	N2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.4	W3	1.2	28.2	54
10	N2	Gravel	Steel	0.8	W6	0.6	26.0	39
11	H1	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.2	W1	0.9	31.0	115
12	H1	Asphalt	Concrete	0.3	W1	1.2	23.0	241
13	H1	Gravel	Steel	0.5	W2	0.8	26.8	75
14	H1	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.3	W2	1.0	26.7	54
15	H1	Gravel	Steel	0.8	W3	0.6	19.8	38
16	H1	Gravel	Steel	0.9	W3	0.6	20.9	64
17	H2	Bridgedeck	Steel	n.a.	n.a.	1.1	33.3	68
18	H2	Bridgedeck	Steel	n.a.	n.a.	1.2	29.5	150
19	H2	Bridgedeck	Steel	n.a.	n.a.	1.2	28.3	197
20	H2	Gravel	Steel	n.a.	n.a.	1.1	23.6	98
21	H2	Bridgedeck	Steel	n.a.	n.a.	1.2	27.0	146
22	H2	Gravel	Steel	n.a.	n.a.	0.9	29.8	215
23	H2	Gravel	Concrete	n.a.	n.a.	1.5	25.8	92
24	H2	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.3	W1	0.9	25.1	99
25	H2	Bridgedeck	Concrete	0.0	W1	1.4	21.4	73
26	H2	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.2	W1	1.0	28.2	125
27	H2	Bridgedeck	Concrete	0.0	W1	1.5	24.6	110
28	H2	Bridgedeck	Concrete	0.0	W1	1.6	25.9	145
29	H2	Bridgedeck	Concrete	0.0	W1	1.5	26.1	192
30	H2	Bridgedeck	Concrete	0.0	W1	1.3	28.6	190
31	H2	Gravel	Concrete	0.4	W1	1.0	28.0	135
32	H2	Gravel	Steel	0.2	W1	1.0	28.1	128
33	H2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.0	W1	1.3	25.1	163
34	H2	Bridgedeck	Concrete	0.0	W1	1.2	23.2	185
35	H2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.0	W1	1.2	28.0	156
36	H2	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.3	W1	1.1	28.0	658
37	H2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.0	W1	1.4	33.0	64
38	H2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.1	W2	1.4	21.6	151
39	H2	Gravel	Concrete	0.1	W2	1.3	21.8	114
40	H2	Gravel	Steel	0.5	W2	0.7	24.7	123
41	H2	Gravel	Steel	0.4	W2	1.0	23.8	141
42	H2	Gravel	Steel	0.2	W2	1.4	29.5	156
43	H2	Gravel	Steel	0.0	W2	1.1	29.3	309
44	H2	Gravel	Concrete	0.1	W2	1.3	22.4	76
45	H2	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.2	W2	1.0	29.0	123
46	H2	Gravel	Steel	0.8	W3	0.6	21.2	56
47	H2	Gravel	Steel	0.5	W3	0.8	24.0	60
48	H2	Asphalt	Concrete	0.0	W3	1.4	24.2	163
49	H2	Gravel	Concrete	0.0	W4	1.4	24.3	232
50	H2	Gravel	Concrete	0.0	W5	1.4	25.0	82
51	H3	Bridgedeck	Steel		n.a.	1.3	29.2	161
52	H3	Bridgedeck	Steel	n.a.	n.a.	1.1	26.9	633
53	H3	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.3	W1	1.0	26.1	123
54	H3	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.3	W1	1.0	26.6	134
55	H3	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.2	W1	1.1	28.7	128
56	H3	Asphalt	Concrete	0.1	W2	1.2	24.2	114
57	H3	Gravel	Steel	0.5	W2	1.2	28.0	82
58	H3	Asphalt	Concrete	0.2	W2	1.4	22.0	92
59	H3	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.1	W3	1.3	30.0	145
60	H3	Gravel	Concrete	0.0	W3	1.5	25.0	72
61	H3	Gravel	Steel	0.3	W4	0.9	22.3	142
62	H4b	Gravel	Steel	n.a.	n.a.	1.6	23.7	139
63	H4b	Gravel	Steel	0.2	n.a.	1.4	20.0	159
64	H4b	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.2	W1	1.1	25.2	71
65	H4b	Bridgedeck	Steel	n.a.	W1	1.1	25.9	105
66	H4b	Bridgedeck	Concrete	0.0	W2	1.2	24.2	279
67	H4b	Gravel	Concrete	0.0	W2	1.5	25.2	478
68	H4b	Gravel	Concrete	0.1	W2	1.3	23.6	120
69	H4b	Gravel	Steel	0.2	W2	1.4	26.6	144
70	H4b	Bridgedeck	Concrete	0.0	W2	1.3	26.8	112
71	H4b	Bridgedeck	Concrete	0	W2	1.3	25.3	121
72	H4b	Gravel	Concrete	0.1	W3	1.3	27.0	109
73	H4b	Bridgedeck	Steel	0.2	W4	1.0	30.0	126

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